

Automated Deformation Mapping in Metal Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

A deformation mapping technique, Automated Deformation Mapping (ADM), has been developed and used to measure deformations on composite material surfaces. The technique employs computer-automated image analysis of a fiducial grid applied to a sample surface. A single monofilament SiC fiber/Ti-6Al-4V composite was sectioned transverse to the fiber axis, and in-plane surface deformations were measured as the sample was loaded in transverse tension. Fiber/matrix separation was detected between 100 and 200 MPa, in agreement with published values [1-4]. The technique was found to be applicable to the measurement of interface separation and matrix flow around a fiber.

INTRODUCTION

Titanium alloy metal matrix composites (MMC's) are being developed for moderately-high temperature use in advanced aircraft turbine engines. One of the potentially limiting issues in monofilament SiC/Ti-alloy composites is the transverse mechanical behavior [5]. The transverse mechanical properties of Ti-alloy MMC's depend greatly upon the mechanical properties at the interface and the matrix flow around the fiber reinforcement [1,6]. The characterization of these microscopic properties is not feasible by macroscopic testing, and though the microscopic behavior has been previously modeled [2,6,7], only a few experimental investigations have been published in this area [1,8,9].

In the SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V system studied here, the interface bond strength is believed to be nearly zero [2], therefore the composite mechanical response is dictated by the matrix properties and the residual clamping stresses on the fiber generated by differential thermal expansion stresses. Reported experimental values for interface separation generally fall near 200 MPa [1,2,4], corresponding to the stress required to overcome the clamping stresses. Sun *et al.* [4] measured interface separation at 266 MPa in a 35 vol. % SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V composite by locating the knee in the stress-strain curve (corresponding to the point at which the fiber no longer bears load). Nimmer, *et al.* [2] detected separation at 200 MPa by measuring replicas of separated interfaces, and extrapolating to zero separation for a composite volume fraction between 25 and 40 vol. %. Marshall, *et al.* [1], using the HASMAP image correlation technique, detected interfacial separation in the range of 120 to 180 MPa, depending on the fiber coating, in a 20 vol. % SCS-6/Ti-25Al-10Nb-3V-1Mo (super α_2) composite.

Matrix flow in SCS-6/Ti-25Al-10Nb-3V-1Mo has been mapped by Marshall, *et al.* [1], who identified several matrix damage mechanisms such as load-axis cracks and transverse cracks. Matrix damage mechanisms were also studied by Jansson, *et al.* [8] and Majumdar, *et al.* [9] on SCS-6/Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn, who found intensive slip bands occurring at 45 degrees with respect to the tensile axis, and final failure to be due to nucleation along these bands.

The goal of the current investigation was to develop a means of characterizing the mechanical response of the interface to tensile loading, and to map flow of the matrix near the fiber in a single fiber composite with the intention of advancing to multi-fiber composites. The technique consists of applying a fiducial grid to the composite surface, imaging the surface at various levels of deformation, digitizing the image, and using custom image analysis software to measure and map displacements across the sample.

A number of other strain mapping techniques were considered for application to MMC systems: While Moiré has excellent strain sensitivity, it lacks the high spatial resolution required to map deformation on the scale of the fiber, which has a diameter of 140 μm [10,11]. Stereoscopy [12,13], though related to ADM in its measurement of feature displacements, is inherently manual, and becomes tedious for large analysis areas. Finally, while naturally-occurring contrast [13] or randomly-applied speckle [14] such as that used in the HASMAP technique [1,3,13] can produce excellent results with superior spatial resolution, the fineness and randomness of the contrast makes tracking large displacements encountered at larger strains difficult. Thus, the ADM technique was designed for a combination of high spatial resolution, good automation and robustness at larger deformations [15].

EXPERIMENTAL

A single Textron® SCS-6 silicon carbide fiber was hot-pressed between two Ti-6Al-4V sheets. The composite was sectioned perpendicular to the fiber axis, producing a 1 mm thick by 3 mm wide by 30 mm long sample. 11 x 25 mm end-tabs were welded to the ends of the sample.

The face with the exposed fiber end was polished until it was optically scratch-free. A fiducial grid was applied by physical vapor deposition (PVD) of a base layer of carbon, followed by PVD evaporation of aluminum onto the sample through a mask comprised of 8.0 μm square holes spaced 12.7 μm apart. The resulting pattern consisted of bright squares, corresponding to aluminum, on a dark background, corresponding to carbon, when viewed in the optical microscope (see Fig. 1).

The sample was deformed in uniaxial tension in the transverse orientation. The sample was incrementally loaded to a pre-determined elongation corresponding to a target matrix stress away from the fiber. This elongation was held constant while optical micrographs of the gridded sample were taken on Polaroid® film. During imaging, the measured load in the sample diminished by about 10 % with time as the matrix relaxed. This process was performed for matrix stresses of 100, 200, 300, 400, 600 and 800 MPa.

The 400X magnification photomicrographs were digitized using a high-resolution digital camera such that the magnification of the digitized images was 6.5 pixels per μm (0.15 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$). Image analysis was used to determine the locations of the grid squares at each stress. The changes in the relative positions of the squares were used to calculate in-plane displacements on the sample surface.

The images were analyzed using custom-written software employing the extremely accurate cross correlation feature location [16,17] to determine the positions of squares in the images of the sample at each level of deformation. In simplified terms, cross correlation can be described as the measurement of the quality of the feature match as a reference image is rastered over the image to be searched. At each point in the raster (each point corresponding to a pixel), the reference intensity values are multiplied by the underlying search area intensity values, and the cross-correlation value is the sum of these products. The cross-correlation value will be a maximum where the feature registration is best.

For computer analysis, cross correlation consists of a pixel-by-pixel multiplication of intensity values of a reference sub-image containing the feature of interest with those of an image to be searched for the same feature. A sum of the products of these intensities is performed for each point within the search area, and this sum will be a maximum where the registration of the features is the best. Eqn. (1) [16] describes the cross correlation:

$$R_f(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x})t(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \quad (1)$$

where $R_f(\mathbf{y})$ is defined as the cross correlation value at point (\mathbf{y}) for functions f and t , which describe the intensities across the search and reference images, respectively, \mathbf{x} spans the reference sub-image and \mathbf{y} spans the search area. The (\mathbf{y}) value for which $R_f(\mathbf{y})$ is a maximum corresponds to the location of the reference image location within the search image.

Software was written to automate the analysis process using a commercial image analysis package. Interpolation of the cross correlation values near the maximum using a two-dimensional second-order polynomial fit enabled sub-pixel feature location. The image of the surface at zero stress was taken as the reference image. This was divided into reference templates, each template encompassing a 2×2 array of grid squares. Each template was correlated to the corresponding area in the deformed image, and displacements were calculated by measuring the change between the reference and deformed images in distance between the upper-left template and the point of interest, as well as by measuring the change in distance between adjacent templates.

Finite element analysis (FEA) modeling was performed using ANSYS [18]. Three-dimensional, eight-node isoparametric elements were used to describe the fiber and matrix, while the interface (i.e., coatings or reaction products) was modeled using three-dimensional eight-node concrete solids as a thin layer with a finite thickness and independent properties. The isoparametric elements could deform plastically, whereas the concrete solids could also crack or be crushed. The cracking capability was necessary at the interface to simulate interface separation. If any principal stress at the interface was tensile, the interface cracked; crushing occurred only if all principal stresses were compressive. When all principal stresses were tensile, the criterion for cracking at the interface was simply based on the magnitudes of the maximum tensile stresses. For other stress states, compressive stresses contributed to the cracking. The criterion for this has been described in detail in references [6,19]. The finite element mesh is shown in Fig. 2.

The SiC fiber was assumed to be isotropic and homogeneous with temperature-independent, linear elastic properties: $E=414$ GPa, $\nu=0.3$ and $\alpha=4.86 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($T_{\text{ref}}=900$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for α) [2]. The Ti-6Al-4V was also assumed to be isotropic and homogeneous, and have the following elastoplastic properties:

$$\sigma_e=113800 \times \epsilon \text{ (MPa)} \quad (\text{elastic regime}) \quad [20] \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_p=881 + 2085 \times \epsilon \text{ (MPa)} \quad (\text{plastic regime}) \quad [2] \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is the true strain, and σ_e and σ_p are the true stresses during elastic and plastic deformation, respectively. The room temperature matrix properties used in this study were measured from neat materials which had undergone the same processing cycle as the composite specimen. The matrix was further assumed to obey the von Mises yield criterion with an isotropic work hardening capability, and to have $\nu = 0.3$ and $\alpha = 9.8 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($T_{\text{ref}} = 900^{\circ}\text{C}$ for α) [21]. The interface was assumed to be weakly bonded with a fracture strength of 5 MPa. This assumption was based on the work conducted by Nimmer, *et al.* [2] who have shown that the interface between Ti-6Al-4V and SCS-6 SiC fiber is very weak due to the presence of the graded carbon/silicon coating.

Both thermal and transverse mechanical loads were considered. Thermal loads were applied under the assumption that the temperature is spatially uniform throughout the composite during cooling. The composite was rapidly cooled from a specific annealing temperature (800°C) to 25°C . Therefore, no time-dependent stress relaxation during the cooling was considered. The zero stress state of the composite was specified to be the annealing temperature, and the first load applied to the composite was the thermal load generated during cooling. After the cooling event, the mechanical load was superimposed on the residual thermal stresses by applying a tensile stress in the X-coordinate direction.

RESULTS

Fig. 3 diagrams the in-plane displacements relative to the upper-left template. The displacements at zero stress are the result of correlation of the reference digital image to itself; the maximum 0.0055 μm displacement is indicative of the small error introduced by the computer analysis. At 100 MPa the maximum displacement is 0.38 μm , however the direction of the displacements is inconsistent with that of the applied load. Further analysis revealed that most of the apparent displacement was due to image distortion in the optical train, a difficulty that has been reported elsewhere [13]. The error was largest at 100 MPa, and had the property of varying continuously and systematically across the analysis area, allowing rational interpretation of the error despite its magnitude. At 200 MPa there is a change in magnitude and sense of the displacement vectors along the interface, perpendicular to the load axis (columns 3 and 4 in Fig. 3). This is not the case at 100 MPa, indicating interface separation between 100 and 200 MPa. Fig. 4 is a plot of the maximum separation between the fiber and matrix as a function of stress, as measured by comparing changes in spacing in adjacent templates along row 6 of the analysis area. The small separation measured at 200 MPa supports the assertion of interface separation between 100 and 200 MPa. By 300 MPa, the fiber has clearly separated from the matrix, and has displaced, more or less as a whole, approximately 0.36 μm from the matrix in the lower-left corner of the analysis area. Matrix flow is just apparent in the matrix in the upper-right corner. From 400 to 800 MPa, the fiber continues to displace from the matrix, reaching a maximum displacement of about 2.4 μm at 800 MPa. At 800 MPa, in addition to continued elongation along the load axis apparent in the upper-right corner, shear of the lower-left corner relative to the upper-left corner is evident.

Fig. 5 is a set of diagrams depicting the FEA results. The FEA-modeled matrix flow differs from the experimental results by approximately 20 %, and otherwise reproduces the flow phenomena divulged by the ADM technique. At high far-field stresses, both ADM and FEA indicate a Poisson contraction (vertical vector component) along column 0 accompanying the strain along the loading direction, most clearly evident the lower-left corner. Also, in the upper-right corner, both matrix regions show larger local strains compared to the upper-left corner. This is presumably due to the enhanced flow along the load axis around the fiber after interface separation, since the fiber can no longer contribute mechanically.

FEA predicts interface separation at 270 MPa, which is significantly more than the experimental results. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the experimental work measured interface separation at a free surface, whereas FEA modeled separation in the bulk. It is known that residual clamping stresses on the fiber are less at a surface, and can in fact be negative (i.e. tensile) [22,23], therefore the stress to separate the interface should be less at a free surface. It should be noted that this separation or debonding stress of 270 MPa is higher than those predicted for $\text{SiC}_f/\text{Ti-6Al-4V}$ composites with 30 vol. SiC [1,2]; this difference is attributable to the higher residual clamping stress at the interface in the single fiber composite than for a 30 vol. % composite.

SUMMARY

In summary, ADM has been shown to be applicable to the study of surface deformations of MMC's. Interface separation in a single fiber $\text{SiC}/\text{Ti-6Al-4V}$ composite was detected between 100 MPa and 200 MPa in uniaxial transverse tension. Matrix flow was mapped in the vicinity of the fiber with a spatial resolution of about 13 μm (i.e., mapping density), and with good displacement sensitivity as evidenced by the detection of interface separation of approximately 0.2 μm . The results agree qualitatively with FEA of a similar sample geometry. While the technique is still being refined, it has demonstrated the desired attributes of good automation, high spatial resolution and displacement sensitivity, and the ability to track large displacements.

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Figure 1. Digitized reference image at zero stress. The size of the correlation template is indicated along with the orientation of the tensile load. The template array locations are indicated by the row and column numbers.

Figure 2. Finite element mesh

Figure 3. Transverse loading displacements of a quadrant of the fiber/matrix relative to the center of the upper-left template. The rows and columns correspond to the reference image templates spaced $12.7\ \mu\text{m}$ apart. The first diagram is a schematic describing the loading direction, the correlation template size, the location of the fiber, and the relation between the displacement vectors and the correlation templates. The other diagrams are displacement maps at increasing levels of stress: note the different scales employed for each diagram.

Figure 4. Maximum interface separation between the fiber and matrix as a function of stress as measured along row 6.

Figure 5. Displacements generated by finite element analysis for the single-fiber composite, plotted in the same format as figure 3 (relative to (0,0)).